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A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE PERFORMANCE OF THE DIPLOMA STUDENTS IN MATHEMATICS IN THE MODERN WORLD

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the students' performances in their Math entrance examination and Math of the Modern World (MMW) subject. These randomly selected students consisted of 146 Senior High School (SHS) graduates, 67 Basic Education Curriculum graduates (BEC), and 63 Alternative Learning System (ALS) graduates. For data treatment, the tools used were percentage, mean, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, and ANOVA. Findings revealed that the entrance examination performance of the SHS and BEC graduates was "average" while the performance of the ALS graduates was "good." Also, these three groups of students had an "average" performance in MMW subject. Furthermore, the study found out that there was a significant difference in the performances of the three groups of students in the entrance examination in favor of the ALS graduates. A significant difference also existed in their performances in MMW subject with SHS graduates performing better than the ALS graduates. Moreover, a significant and moderate relationship existed between the entrance examination performance of the BEC and ALS graduates and their performance in MMW subject.

Keywords: *entrance exam, performance in Math of the Modern World, diploma students, Alternative Learning Systems (ALS), Basic Education Curriculum (BEC), Senior High School (SHS)*

INTRODUCTION

Education is regarded as the most essential tool for attaining success in life. It equips individuals with the right mindset to step forward, excel in their endeavors, and create a positive impact so that they can acquire recognition. Moreover, it provides everyone the ability to think critically, get better decisions to cope with different life challenges, and motivate others so they too can grow on their own chosen path (Dizon et al., 2019).

Abueva (2019) posited that implementing the K-12 Program in the Philippine Curriculum of Basic Education is the key to the growth of the country. Although there have been several problems in terms of its implementation, the K-12 program remains a necessity so that the nation can increase the quality of its education. To meet the needs of the global market where quality education is a must for everyone, the Philippine Educational system adopted a modern and more dynamic curriculum that follows the 12-year program. The K-12 program is aimed at producing more skilled students who have the basic skills necessary for lifelong learning and employment. It also promotes the recognition of Filipino learners and professionals in other countries.

However, illiteracy has been noted as the biggest obstacle to a country's economic growth. Southeast Asian and African countries, for example, have been bombarded with economic crisis brought about by poverty, which is associated with illiteracy. The Philippines has also been tagged as one of the countries that have the highest poverty incidence rates in Southeast Asia. Furthermore, the Out-of-School Children (OSC), Out-of-School Youth (OSYs), and Out-of-School Adults (OSAs) are seen as the most affected by poverty due to the lack of educational opportunities (Apao *et al.*, 2014).

To alleviate the issue, the Alternative Learning System (ALS) was established. ALS is a parallel learning system that is combined with non-formal education and informal sources of knowledge and skills. It is designed to provide all Filipinos the chance to have access to and complete their basic education in a way that fits their distinct situations and needs (DepEd, 2016). The diploma program is supported by Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), wherein scholars can avail of a free tuition fee, learning materials allowance, internet allowance, personal protective equipment (PPE) allowance, and 160 pesos allowance per day. It is also anchored on Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) program *Abot Lahat* whose purpose is to expand and strengthen its mandate and services to all, to reach out and serve new partners and clients with a clear objective, and to transform and improve lives for the better (TESDA, 2015).

In this regard, the researcher of the current study wanted to further investigate how the graduates of ALS, BEC, and SHS are faring academically. Although some researches already examined the performance of students who graduated from BEC, SHS, and ALS, no one studied on the comparison of the performances of these three groups of student graduates.

In conclusion, Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) in partnership with educational institutions offers scholarship and caters to the aforementioned groups of graduates. Thus, the researcher decided to pursue this study with the intent to identify and compare the performances of these diploma students.

Research Questions

This study sought to compare the three groups of diploma students' academic performances in the Mathematics in the Modern World Subject. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the performance of the following groups of students in the entrance examination in Mathematics:
 - 1.1.1 K to 12 Senior High School Graduates (SHS);
 - 1.1.2 Basic Education Curriculum Graduates (BEC); and
 - 1.1.3 Alternative Learning System Graduates (ALS)?
 2. What is the performance of following groups of students in Mathematics of the Modern World subject?
 - 2.1.1 K to 12 Senior High School Graduates (SHS);
 - 2.1.2 Basic Education Curriculum Graduates (BEC); and
 - 2.1.3 Alternative Learning System Graduates (ALS)?
 3. Is there a significant difference in the performance of the 3 groups of respondents in the following:
 - 3.1 Entrance examination; and
 - 3.2 Mathematics in the Modern World subject?
 4. Is there a significant relationship between the entrance examination results of the students and their performance in the Mathematics in the Modern World subject?
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METHODOLOGY

Data and Respondents

The study used the descriptive-comparative method of research. It is descriptive in the sense that the results of entrance examination and the performance of the three groups of students are described. It is also comparative since the study compared the Math performance of these three groups of respondents and their performance in the entrance examination.

The respondents of the study were the 276 diploma students of Metro Dumaguete College for the academic year 2020-2021. They were chosen using a systematic sampling technique wherein every second student in the list is included.

The following data reflect the distribution of the respondents.

Curriculum/Program	Population (N)	Sample (n)
Alternative Learning System (ALS) Graduate	75	63
Senior High School (SHS) Graduate	200	146
Basic Education Curriculum Graduate (BEC)	100	67
Total	375	276

The data-gathering process concerning students' grades and scores in the entrance examination was conducted in Metro Dumaguete College. Metro Dumaguete College is situated in E.J Blanco Extension, Daro Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental. Being one of the private schools in this so-called "university town," it offers quality education with emphasis on the use of technology. The school has enough learning facilities including Wi-Fi and laboratories. It offers a Senior High School program, as well as TESDA-accredited Technical Vocational courses and four-year college courses. The growing school community necessitated a much larger campus, prompting the administration to seek for a larger and better facility to provide to its consumers.

The Diploma in Tourism Technology, Diploma in Digital Arts Technology, and Diploma in Software Engineering Technology all offered at Metro Dumaguete College. These TESDA courses are integrated into the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) curriculum and are funded by Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) to offer students a three-year scholarship.

The researcher used the data depicting the students' performance in the college entrance examination and in Mathematics in the Modern World subject. The Math items were extracted from the Metro Dumaguete College entrance examination.

All the necessary ethical considerations were observed by the researcher during the entire duration of the study. Confidentiality was observed to ensure privacy of the information extracted from the respondents. The researcher also adhered to the ethical protocols stipulated in the Ethics Committee of Foundation University. In addition, the researcher sought permission from the proper authorities before conducting the study.

A written letter was first sent to the school President of Metro Dumaguete College to request for permission to allow the researcher to conduct the study in the campus. After gaining approval of the request, copies of the approved letter were then given to the Vice President of Academic Affairs for the researcher to be allowed to get from the registrar department the data with regard to the students' grades in Mathematics in the Modern World and their entrance examination scores. Afterwards, the results were tabulated and tallied using the MS Excel and then analyzed and interpreted.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The tools used in analyzing and interpreting the data are the following:

Percentage. This is used to show how a part is related to a whole. In the study, this was used in presenting the profile of the student.

Mean. This was used to show the student's performance in the entrance examination and in Mathematics in the Modern World. The grading system used by Metro Dumaguete College, which consists of the Midterm Exam (40%) and the Final Exam (60%), serves as the basis for the scores.

Numerical Grade	Percentage Rating	Description
1.0	100	Excellent
1.1	98-99	Excellent
1.2	96-97	Excellent
1.3	94-95	Excellent
1.4	92-93	Very Good
1.5	90-91	Very Good
1.6	89	Very Good
1.7	88	Very Good
1.8	87	Good
1.9	86	Good
2.0	85	Good
2.1	84	Good
2.2	83	Average
2.3	82	Average
2.4	81	Average
2.5	80	Average
2.6	79	Below Average
2.7	78	Below Average
2.8	77	Below Average
2.9	76	Below Average
3.0	75	Passing
5.0	74	Failed
OD	OD	Officially Dropped
INC	INC	Incomplete

Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation. This was used in determining the relationship between the entrance examination scores of the students and their performance in the Mathematics in the Modern World subject. This statistical tool is applicable since the data are classified as ratio scale.

To describe the strength of relationship between the variables, the researcher used the following scale (Statistical Correlation, 2009):

Legend:	Value of r			Strength of Relationship
Between	± 0.50 to	± 1.00	-	strong relationship
Between	± 0.30 to	± 0.49	-	moderate relationship
Between	± 0.10 to	± 0.29	-	weak relationship
Between	± 0.01 to	± 0.09	-	very weak relationship

Analysis of Variance. This was used in identifying the significant difference in the performances of the three groups of respondents in the entrance examination and in Mathematics in the Modern World subject.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the performance of the three groups of students in Mathematics entrance examination. The data reveal that the mean performance of Senior High School (SHS) graduates is 80.34% and the Basic Education Curriculum (BEC) graduates is 82.21%. Both ratings are classified as “average” performance. This means that these graduates have developed the fundamental knowledge, skills, and core understandings in Mathematics and they need only little guidance from the teacher or with some assistance from peers (DepEd Order No. 73, s. 2012).

Meanwhile, the data also expose that ALS graduates have a mean performance of 86.03%, which is classified as a “good” performance. This means that the students at this level have developed the fundamental knowledge, skills, and core understandings of Mathematics, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks (DepEd Order No. 73, s. 2012).

The above finding contradicts that of Remo’s (2019) results. She revealed that students in her study did not perform well in their entrance examination test since most students have conditional status.

College admission exams are standardized examinations that determine students’ chance of pursuing a degree in an academic institution (Bai *et al.*, 2014). As Gomez *et al.* (2012) stressed that a good admission test can predict the students’ academic ability to succeed in his/her chosen program.

Table 1

Performance of the Three Groups of Students in the Entrance Examination in Math

Rating	Verbal Description	Senior High School Graduate (n = 146)		BEC Graduate (n = 67)		ALS Graduate (n = 63)	
		f	%	f	%	f	%
94% - 100%	Excellent	28	19.18	15	22.39	18	28.57
88% - 93%	Very Good	21	14.38	6	8.96	12	19.05
84% - 87%	Good	7	4.80	7	10.45	9	14.29
80% - 83%	Average	9	6.16	9	13.43	9	14.29
76% - 79%	Below Average	15	10.27	9	13.43	5	7.93
75%	Passing	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
≤74%	Failed	66	45.21	21	31.34	10	15.87
Total		146	100.00	67	100.00	63	100.00
Mean		80.34 (Average)		82.21 (Average)		86.03 (Good)	
sd		10.98		10.57		9.66	

Table 2 shows the performance of the three groups of students in Mathematics in the Modern Word (MMW) subject. It divulges that the mean performances of the SHS, BEC, and ALs graduates are 82.23%, 81.82%, and 80.44%, respectively. These ratings are categorized as “average” performance. This means that the three groups of graduates have developed the fundamental knowledge, skills, and core understandings in MMW subject. They can also transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks (DepEd Order No. 73, s. 2012). This finding is in line with that of Remo (2019). She indicated that most of the students (44%) in MMW have a fair performance with ratings between 80% - 82%.

Table 2

Performance of the Three Groups of Students in Math of the Modern World Subject

Rating	Verbal Description	Senior High School Graduate (n = 146)		BEC Graduate (n = 67)		ALS Graduate (n = 63)	
		f	%	f	%	f	%
94% -100%	Excellent	2	1.37	1	1.49	0	0.00
88% - 93%	Very Good	12	8.22	8	11.94	5	7.94
84% - 87%	Good	39	26.71	12	17.9	9	14.28
80% - 83%	Average	63	43.15	25	37.3	26	41.27
76% - 79%	Below Average	20	13.70	12	17.9	15	23.81
75%	Passing	10	6.85	9	13.4	8	12.70
Total		146	100.0	67		63	100.00
Mean		82.23		81.82		80.44	
sd		4.13		4.92		4.08	

Table 3.1 presents the data identifying the difference in the performances of the three groups of students in the entrance examination. It shows that the mean performances of the three groups of students differ numerically. To test the data statistically, ANOVA test was applied. Results revealed that the computed p-value (0.002) is less than the level of significance (0.05). This finding allows rejection of the null hypothesis. In other words, a significant difference exists among the mean performances of the three groups of students. To test which group is better than the other, a post hoc analysis was applied. The results are presented in Table 3.2.

Table 3.1

Analysis Table on the Difference in the Performance of the Three Groups of Students in the Entrance Examination

Groups of Students	N	Mean	F	p-value	Decision	Remark
Senior High School Graduate	146	80.34				
BEC Graduate	67	82.21	6.35	0.002	Reject	Significant
ALS Graduate	63	86.03			H ₀₁	

Level of Significance (α) = 0.05

Table 3.2 shows that the entrance examination performance of the SHS graduates is as good as that of BEC graduates ($p = 0.234 > \alpha = 0.05$). It also reveals that the ALS graduates perform better than the SHS graduates ($p = 0.004 < \alpha = 0.05$). Furthermore, the ALS graduates have a higher performance than the BEC Curriculum graduates ($p = 0.041 < \alpha = 0.05$). This is parallel to the findings of Mercado (2015) who postulated that the ALS in Tanauan had minimal problems in the assessment and evaluation.

Table 3.2
Post Hoc Analysis on the Difference in the Performance of the Three Groups of Students in the Entrance Examination

Paired Variables	p-value	Decision	Remark
SHS vs BEC $\bar{x}_1 = 80.34$; $\bar{x}_2 = 82.21$	0.234	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
SHS vs ALS $\bar{x}_1 = 80.34$; $\bar{x}_3 = 86.03$	0.004	Reject H_{01}	Significant
BEC vs ALS $\bar{x}_2 = 82.21$; $\bar{x}_3 = 86.03$	0.041	Reject H_{01}	Significant

Level of Significance (α) = 0.05

Table 3.3 contains the data identifying the difference in the performances of the three groups of students in their Mathematics in the Modern World subject. It manifests that the computed p-value (0.024) is less than the level of significance (0.05). This finding warrants rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that a significant difference exists among the mean performances of the three groups of students. To test which group is better than the other, a post hoc analysis was applied. The results are presented in Table 3.4.

Table 3.3
Analysis Table on the Difference in the Performance of the Three Groups of Students in the Mathematics in the Modern World Subject

Groups of Students			n	Mean	F	p-value	Decision	Remark
Senior High School Graduate			146	82.23	3.78	0.024	Reject H_{01}	Significant
BEC Graduate			67	81.82				
ALS Graduate			63	80.44				

Level of Significance (α) = 0.05

Table 3.4 exposes that the SHS graduates' performance in the Math in the Modern World subject is as good as that of BEC graduates ($p = 0.519 > \alpha = 0.05$). It also divulges that SHS graduates performed better than the ALS graduates ($p = 0.007 < \alpha = 0.05$). Furthermore, BEC graduates have more or less the same performance with the ALS graduates ($p = 0.071 > \alpha = 0.05$).

Table 3.4

Post Hoc Analysis on the Difference in the Performance of the Three Groups of Students in the Mathematics in the Modern World Subject

Paired Variables	p-value	Decision	Remark
SHS vs BEC $\bar{x}_1 = 82.23$; $\bar{x}_2 = 81.82$	0.519	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
SHS vs ALS $\bar{x}_1 = 82.23$; $\bar{x}_3 = 80.44$	0.007	Reject H_{01}	Significant
BEC vs ALS $\bar{x}_2 = 81.82$; $\bar{x}_3 = 80.44$	0.071	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant

Level of Significance (α) = 0.05

Table 4 presents the data identifying the relationship between the performance of the three groups of students in the entrance examination and in Mathematics in the Modern World subject. The data show that the entrance examination performance of the SHS graduates is not significantly related to their performance in Mathematics in the Modern World subject ($p = 0.772 > \alpha = 0.05$). In other words, their prior performance is not a predictor of their performance in Mathematics in the Modern World.

Metli and Özcan (2021) support the current finding. In their study, they found that there is no statistically significant correlation between International Baccalaureate Diploma Program (IBDP) scores and university entrance exam. A similar finding was obtained by HE *et al.* (2015) who claimed that there were no significant correlations between the mathematics test scores in the entrance examination and the academic performance in many subjects.

The present data also point out that the entrance examination performance of the BEC graduates is significantly and moderately ($r = 0.300$) related to their performance in the Mathematics in the Modern World subject ($p = 0.013 < \alpha = 0.05$). This means that the higher the performance of the BEC graduates is in the entrance examination, the higher also is their performance in Mathematics in the Modern World subject.

This result is evident in the study of Fabito *et al.* (2015) who emphasized that the student entrance examination of the National University-Manila is directly correlated with the students' academic performance in the College of Computer and Information Technologies.

Additionally, the data also show that the entrance examination performance of the ALS graduates is significantly and moderately ($r = 0.426$) related to their performance in the Mathematics in the Modern World subject ($p = 0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$). This means that the ALS graduates who have better performance in the entrance examination tend to also exhibit higher performance in the Mathematics in the Modern World subject. This further

implies that the performance of the ALS graduates in entrance examination influences their performance in the Mathematics in the Modern World subject.

Bai *et al.* (2014) support the current finding. In their study, they found that a strong correlation exists between the students' entrance examination and their undergraduate grade point average. In reverse, Agazade *et al.* (2014) found a low correlation between students' academic performance and their entrance exam test.

Table 4
Relationship between the Performance of the Three Groups of Students in Entrance Examination and in Math in the Modern World Subject

Groups of Students	n	r	p-value	Decision	Remark
SHS Graduates	146	0.024	0.772	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not significant
BEC Graduates	67	0.300	0.013	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
ALS Graduates	63	0.426	0.000	Reject H ₀₂	Significant

Level of Significance (α) = 0.05

Legend: **Value of r** **Strength of Relationship** (Statistical Correlation, 2009)

Between	± 0.50 to ± 1.00	± strong relationship
Between	± 0.30 to ± 0.49	± moderate relationship
Between	± 0.10 to ± 0.29	± weak relationship
Between	± 0.01 to ± 0.09	± very weak relationship

Table 1
Performance of the Three Groups of Students in the Entrance Examination in Math

Rating	Verbal Description	Senior High School Graduate (n = 146)		BEC Graduate (n = 67)		ALS Graduate (n = 63)	
		f	%	f	%	f	%
94% - 100%	Excellent	28	19.18	15	22.39	18	28.57
88% - 93%	Very Good	21	14.38	6	8.96	12	19.05
84% - 87%	Good	7	4.80	7	10.45	9	14.29
80% - 83%	Average	9	6.16	9	13.43	9	14.29
76% - 79%	Below Average	15	10.27	9	13.43	5	7.93
75%	Passing	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
≤74%	Failed	66	45.21	21	31.34	10	15.87
Total		146	100.00	67	100.00	63	100.00
Mean		80.34 (Average)		82.21 (Average)		86.03 (Good)	
sd		10.98		10.57		9.66	

Conclusions

Based on the data collected in this investigation, the following findings are hereby presented:

1. The entrance examination performance of the SHS and BEC graduates is “average” while ALS graduates’ entrance examination performance is “good.”
2. The Mathematics in the Modern World performance of the SHS, BEC, and ALS graduates is in the “average” level.
3. a) There is a significant difference in the performances of the three groups of students in the entrance examination in favor of the ALS graduates; and
b) There is a significant difference in the performances of the three groups of students in the Mathematics in the Modern World subject with SHS graduates performing better than the ALS graduates.
4. A significant and moderate relationship exists between the entrance examination performance of the BEC and ALS graduates and their performance in the Mathematics in the Modern World subject.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions presented, the following are recommended to instructors and school administrators:

1. Process and analyze statistically the results of the entrance examination in order to provide remediation activities to students who have low performance. This will prepare more the students in learning Mathematics of the Modern World subject.
2. Provide feedback to students’ performance in the entrance examination for them to be aware of the results and be able to realize their strengths and weaknesses in Mathematics. This will enable them to find ways to improve their performance.
3. Monitor and provide assistance and attention to students enrolled in Mathematics of the Modern World in order to improve their performance from “average” level to “good” or even “excellent” performance.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

For the length of the study, the researcher will demonstrate all relevant ethical principles. The confidentiality of the information will be preserved because humans will be the study’s subjects.

All the necessary ethical considerations were observed by the researcher during the entire duration of the study. Confidentiality was observed to ensure privacy of the information extracted from the respondents. The researcher also adhered to the ethical protocols stipulated in the Ethics Committee of Foundation University. In addition, the researcher sought permission from the proper authorities before conducting the study.

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REFERENCES

- Abueva, A., (2019). Why Does the Philippines Need the K-12 Education System? Retrieved from <https://soapboxie.com/social-issues/The-Implementation-o-the-K-12-Program-in-the-Philippine-Basic-Education-Curriculum>.
- Ağazade, A. S.; Caner, H.; Hasipoğlu, H. N. & Civelek, A. H. (2014), 'Turkish University Entrance Test and Academic Achievement in Undergraduate Programs: A Criterionrelated Validity Study', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 116, 4582 - 4590.
- Apao, L., Dayagbil, F., and Abao, E. (2014). Alternative Learning System Accreditation and Equivalency (ALS A&E) Program: Quality of Life beyond Poverty. *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Innovations* Vol. 2, Issue 4, pp: (20-26), Month: October - December 2014 Retrieved from www.researchjournals.com
- Bai, C. E., Chi, W., & Qian, X. (2014). Do college entrance examination scores predict undergraduate GPAs? A tale of two universities. *China Economic Review*, 30, 632-647.
- Department of Education (2016). Why is there a need for Alternative Learning System in the Philippines? Retrieved from <http://www.deped.gov.ph/als>.
- Dizon R. L., Calbi J. S., Cuyos J. S., Miranda M. PhD. (2019, 12 April). *Perspectives on the Implementation of the K to 12 Program in the Philippines: A Research Review*. https://www.ijires.org/administrator/components/com_jresearch/files/publications/IJIRES_1638_FINAL.pdf.
- Fabito, B. S., Rodriguez, R. L., & Catacutan-Bangit, A. E. (2015). Correlation between student entrance exam results and academic performance: Case of a College in a Philippine University.
- Gómez-López, V., Rosales-Gracia, S., Marín-Solórzano, G., & Josefina Guzmán-Acuña, C. (2012). Correlation between the entrance exam and the academic performance at the end of the medical career. *Revista Cubana de Educacion Medica Superior*, 502-513.
- HE, S., KEMPE, K., Tomiki, Y., NISHIZUKA, M., SUZUKI, T., DAMBARA, T., & OKADA, T. (2015). Correlations between entrance examination scores and academic performance following admission. *Juntendo Medical Journal*, 61(2), 142-148.
- Metli, A., & Özcan, O. (2021). Relationship Between Achievement Performances of University Entrance Examination and International Baccalaureate Diploma

- Program: A Case from Turkey. *International Journal of Educational Reform*, 30(3), 255-266.
- Remo, L. M. (2019). Prediction and assessment of students' performance in Mathematics in the Modern World (MMW). *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 8(4), 219-224.
- Statistical Correlation (2009). <https://explorable.com/statistical-correlation>
- Explorable.com (May 2, 2009). Statistical Correlation. Retrieved Oct 25, 2016 from Explorable.com: <https://explorable.com/statistical-correlation>
- Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA). (2020, 13 October). *Omnibus Guidelines on Packaging Rules of PQF Level 5 (Diploma) Programs for the TVET Sector*. <https://www.scribd.com/document/491228352/TESDA-Circular-No-119-2020>.